

RMSTpowerBoost: Power and Sample Size Calculation for Covariate-Adjusted Restricted Mean Survival Time

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Abstract

The R package `RMSTpowerBoost` and its companion Shiny application provide a unified framework for power and sample size calculations based on the restricted mean survival time (RMST) as a measure for time-to-event outcomes. The package enhances statistical efficiency by allowing covariate adjustment through flexible, direct RMST modeling. The software implements both analytical and simulation-based algorithms and accommodates a wide range of study designs and data complexities, including stratified designs, nonproportional hazards, nonlinear covariate effects, and dependent censoring. This article presents the underlying methodology, describes the package architecture, and illustrates practical workflows with reproducible examples.

Keywords: survival analysis, nonproportional hazards, power analysis, covariate adjustment, R

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1 Introduction

The restricted mean survival time (RMST) has emerged as a robust and interpretable clinical endpoint for summarizing time-to-event outcomes, serving as an alternative to hazard ratio. Defined as the expected survival time up to a fixed truncation point L , the RMST represents the average event-free time within a clinically meaningful window. Essentially, it remains well defined regardless of the underlying hazard function. Its practical relevance was first highlighted in covariate-adjusted settings by Karrison (1987) and later generalized through the work of Royston and Parmar (2011). Subsequent advances have extended RMST methodology to regression frameworks (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen, 2010; Tian et al., 2014). Together, these developments have positioned RMST as a flexible and reliable estimand.

The proportional hazards (PH) assumption has long underpinned survival analysis via the Cox model. However, growing empirical evidence suggests that this assumption is often violated in modern biomedical studies, particularly when treatment effects vary over time or event rates differ across subpopulations. Such violations undermine the interpretability of the hazard ratio and may invalidate standard power and sample size calculations based on the log-rank test. Moreover, the hazard ratio generally lacks a clear causal interpretation (Martinussen et al., 2020), limiting its usefulness for assessing treatment effects.

Despite methodological progress, software tools for the *design* of RMST-based studies remain limited. Packages such as `survRM2` (Uno et al., 2014) and `focus` on estimation and model fitting, whereas design-oriented utilities like `powerSurvEpi` assume proportional hazards and are therefore not directly applicable to RMST endpoints. Existing packages for sample size calculation, such as `SSRMST` (Horiguchi and Uno, 2017) and `RMSTdesign` (Eaton et al., 2020), focus on marginal treatment effect. The statistical software `PASS` (pas, 2026) for general sample size calculation has limited functions in survival analysis. As a result, researchers interested in simulation-based power analysis or sample size planning under nonproportional hazards often rely on custom scripts or ad hoc combinations of software.

The `RMSTpowerBoost` package addresses this gap by providing a unified framework for RMST-based study design. Its main features include:

- a simulation engine for generating survival data under a wide range of censoring mechanisms and hazard structures, including stratified and covariate-dependent models;
- analytic and Monte Carlo tools for computing statistical power, sample size, and RMST differences at user-defined truncation times;
- built-in visualization tools for summarizing power curves, RMST trajectories, and survival distributions; and
- an interactive `Shiny` interface that facilitates real-time exploration of design parameters for users without programming expertise.

Methodologically, `RMSTpowerBoost` extends the inference principles of Uno et al. (2014) into a simulation-driven design framework that accommodates stratification and dependent censoring (Wang and Schaubel, 2018). Practically, it enables researchers and educators to perform reproducible, RMST-based design studies without manual coding, thereby strengthening the connection between methodological advances in survival analysis and their implementation in applied research.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief overview of RMST-based inference. Section 4 describes the structure and functionality of the `RMSTpowerBoost` package. Section 5 illustrates its application through reproducible examples. Finally, Section 6 concludes with a discussion of future directions.

2 RMST-Based Inference

Restricted mean survival time (RMST) has gained prominence as a flexible and interpretable summary measure in survival analysis, particularly when the proportional hazards (PH) assumption is questionable. This section outlines the conceptual foundation of RMST, its relevance under nonproportional hazards, and its use in covariate-adjusted modeling and simulation-based study design. We begin by contrasting RMST-based inference with the conventional hazard ratio framework.

2.1 Definition of Restricted Mean Survival Time

Let T denote a nonnegative survival time with survival function

$$S(t) = \Pr(T > t), \quad t \geq 0.$$

For a given truncation time $L > 0$, the *restricted mean survival time* (RMST) is defined as the expected event-free time up to L :

$$\mu(L) = \mathbb{E}[\min(T, L)] = \int_0^L S(t) dt. \quad (1)$$

This quantity captures the average survival time within a clinically relevant horizon. Its complement, $\mathbb{E}[(L - T)_+]$, represents the expected loss in survival before L . Unlike the mean lifetime, which may diverge when $S(t)$ decays slowly, the RMST is always finite for any fixed L .

2.2 Conditional RMST and Covariate Effects

In the presence of baseline covariates $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^p$, the *conditional* RMST is given by

$$\mu(L | \mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{E}[\min(T, L) | \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}] = \int_0^L S(t | \mathbf{x}) dt, \quad (2)$$

where $S(t | \mathbf{x})$ denotes the conditional survival function. Equation (2) yields a directly interpretable quantity: the expected event-free time up to L for individuals with covariate profile \mathbf{x} under a specified treatment or exposure. Comparisons of $\mu(L | \mathbf{x})$ across treatment groups represent conditional treatment effects that are free from PH assumptions.

Several modeling strategies have been proposed for $\mu(L | \mathbf{x})$. Pseudo-observation methods (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen, 2010) treat RMST as an outcome in regression models, enabling the use of generalized linear or additive structures. Covariate-adjusted extensions support stratified models and allow for covariate-dependent censoring (Wang and Schaubel, 2018). In simulation studies, $S(t | \mathbf{x})$ may be generated from parametric families (e.g., Weibull, log-normal) or constructed via piecewise exponential hazards.

2.3 Limitations of the Proportional Hazards Framework

The hazard ratio can be difficult to interpret when the PH assumption is violated (Royston and Parmar, 2011, 2013). In particular, if treatment effects vary over time or if survival curves of two groups cross, the hazard ratio becomes a time-dependent, model-specific quantity that may even change direction across the follow-up period.

Figure 1 illustrates these scenarios through panel 1a and panel 1b. In panel 1a, the PH assumption holds, yielding a constant hazard ratio and a consistent interpretation across time. In panel 1b, hazards cross; early treatment effects may differ in direction from later ones. The hazard ratio then varies over follow-up and becomes difficult to interpret as a single summary measure, while the RMST difference remains well defined and clinically interpretable.

(a) PH assumption satisfied: hazards are proportional, and the RMST difference reflects the same trend as the log-rank test.

(b) PH assumption violated: hazards cross over time, so a single hazard ratio is difficult to interpret. The RMST difference remains well defined.

Figure 1: Restricted mean survival time (RMST) under proportional (left) and nonproportional (right) hazard structures. The shaded area below each survival curve up to truncation time L corresponds to the RMST, as defined in Equation (1). In nonproportional settings, the RMST difference $\Delta(L)$ in Equation (3) continues to provide an interpretable summary contrast.

2.4 Inference via Difference in RMST

Inference based on the restricted mean survival time typically focuses on the contrast between treatment arms. Consider a two-arm study comparing treatments A and B , with respective RMSTs $\mu_A(L)$ and $\mu_B(L)$. The treatment effect is defined as the difference

$$\Delta(L) = \mu_A(L) - \mu_B(L), \quad (3)$$

which quantifies the average gain in event-free time provided by treatment A relative to B up to truncation time L . Estimates of $\mu(L)$ are obtained by numerically integrating the Kaplan–Meier estimator of the survival function $S(t)$ within each arm. The corresponding variance can be derived using Greenwood’s formula applied to the estimated survival curve, or alternatively through pseudo-observation regression methods (Tian et al., 2014). Tests of the null hypothesis $H_0: \Delta(L) = 0$ form the basis of RMST-based group comparisons, as implemented in the `RMSTpowerBoost` package.

To improve efficiency and adjust for baseline covariates, the unadjusted contrast in Equation (3) can be extended to a conditional framework. Let \mathbf{Z} denote a vector of baseline covariates, and define the conditional RMST as

$$\mu(L | A, \mathbf{Z}) = \mathbb{E}[\min(T, L) | A, \mathbf{Z}].$$

A convenient working regression model is specified as

$$\mu(L | A, \mathbf{Z}) = m_L(A, \mathbf{Z}; \beta) = \alpha + \tau A + \mathbf{Z}^\top \gamma, \quad (4)$$

where τ represents the treatment effect at horizon L , interpreted as the conditional difference in expected event-free time between treatments for individuals with identical covariate profiles \mathbf{Z} . Equation (4) is the working template that later becomes the model-specific mean structure in Section 3.2. The remaining parameters α and γ describe the baseline RMST and covariate effects, respectively.

Estimation proceeds via inverse probability of censoring weighting (IPCW) or pseudo-observation regression to account for right censoring (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen,

2010; Tian et al., 2014). Under random treatment assignment and correct model specification, the estimated coefficient τ coincides with the marginal RMST difference $\Delta(L)$ in Equation (3). Parameter estimation is typically performed using weighted least squares on pseudo-observations, and Wald tests for $H_0: \tau = 0$ employ robust (sandwich) standard errors.

When proportional hazards assumptions are violated or censoring mechanisms are complex, analytic power approximations may be less reliable. In such settings, simulation-based approaches—as implemented in the `RMSTpowerBoost` package—provide a practical way to evaluate statistical power and determine sample size requirements across a wide range of study designs. Building on these concepts, we next detail the concrete regression formulations and weighting schemes used in practice. Section 3 specifies the implemented models, estimation equations, and variance calculations that underpin the software.

3 Statistical Background and Implemented Models

The `RMSTpowerBoost` package is built around a common statistical framework for modeling the restricted mean survival time (RMST) under right censoring, stratification, and complex covariate structures. This section outlines the main estimators and regression formulations implemented in the software, emphasizing their interconnections through a common conditional mean representation. The exposition moves from the IPCW construction in Section 3.1 to the model classes in Section 3.2, with the stratified family collected in Section 3.2.2: the linear specification in Section 3.2.1, the additive and multiplicative stratified formulations in Sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.2, the GAM extension in Section 3.2.3, and the dependent-censoring adjustment in Section 3.2.4. The general model is

$$\mu(L | A, \mathbf{Z}) = \mathbb{E}[\min(T, L) | A, \mathbf{Z}], \quad (5)$$

where T denotes the survival time, $A \in \{0, 1\}$ is the treatment indicator, \mathbf{Z} is a vector of baseline covariates, and L is the truncation time. Equation (5) is the common target across all implemented regression interfaces. The treatment effect (TE) at horizon L is denoted by τ and represents the conditional difference in expected event-free time between treatment arms.

3.1 Inverse Probability of Censoring Weighting (IPCW)

In the presence of right censoring, the full survival time T may not be observed. Let C denote the censoring time and define $Y = \min(T, C)$ as the observed follow-up time, with event indicator $\Delta = I(T \leq C)$. Estimation of RMST and its regression parameters relies on weighting each observation by the inverse probability of remaining uncensored up to Y . Let $G(t) = P(C > t)$ denote the survival function of the censoring distribution, estimated nonparametrically (e.g., Kaplan–Meier) or via a Cox/stratified model. The IPCW for subject i is

$$w_i = \frac{\Delta_i}{\hat{G}(Y_i)}, \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{G}(Y_i)$ is the estimated probability of being uncensored beyond Y_i . This weighting ensures unbiased estimation of expectations involving $\min(T, L)$ under independent censoring (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen, 2010; Tian et al., 2014). All regression models below incorporate these weights.

3.2 Implemented survival regression models

3.2.1 Linear model

The foundational covariate-adjusted model assumes a linear relationship between the conditional RMST and covariates:

$$\mu(L | A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i) = \alpha + \tau A_i + \mathbf{Z}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}. \quad (7)$$

Here, τ represents the treatment effect at horizon L , interpreted as the conditional difference in expected event-free time for individuals with identical covariate profiles. Estimation is based on the IPCW-weighted least squares criterion

$$\min_{\alpha, \tau, \boldsymbol{\gamma}} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \left\{ Y_i - (\alpha + \tau A_i + \mathbf{Z}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}) \right\}^2, \quad (8)$$

where $Y_i = \min(T_i, C_i, L)$ and w_i is defined in Equation (6). Under correct model specification, $\hat{\tau}$ consistently estimates τ , with asymptotic variance obtained via a robust (sandwich) estimator. An equivalent implementation replaces Y_i by pseudo-observations (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen, 2010) with unit weights.

3.2.2 Stratified models for multi-center trials

When data arise from multiple centers or strata, baseline risks may differ. Let $j = 1, \dots, J$ index strata, and let S_j indicate membership in stratum j . The stratified formulation extends Equation (7) by allowing stratum-specific baselines while retaining a common treatment effect τ .

Additive stratified model. Treatment and covariate effects are additive and constant across strata, while each stratum has its own baseline RMST:

$$\mu_{ij}(L) = \mu_{0j}(L) + \tau A_{ij} + \mathbf{Z}_{ij}^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mu_{0j}(L)$ denotes the baseline RMST for stratum j . Estimation proceeds via IPCW-weighted least squares:

$$\min_{\{\mu_{0j}(L)\}, \tau, \boldsymbol{\gamma}} \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{i \in S_j} w_{ij} \left\{ Y_{ij} - (\mu_{0j}(L) + \tau A_{ij} + \mathbf{Z}_{ij}^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}) \right\}^2. \quad (10)$$

Multiplicative stratified model. Alternatively, Wang et al. (2019) model treatment and covariate effects as multiplicative on the baseline RMST:

$$\mu_{ij}(L) = \mu_{0j}(L) \exp(\tau A_{ij} + \mathbf{Z}_{ij}^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}), \quad (11)$$

or equivalently,

$$\log\{\mu_{ij}(L)\} = \log\{\mu_{0j}(L)\} + \tau A_{ij} + \mathbf{Z}_{ij}^\top \boldsymbol{\gamma}.$$

Formal estimation requires an iterative solver for the estimating equations of Wang et al. (2019); in the software implementation, a log-linear working model fitted by weighted least squares to pseudo-observations serves as a tractable approximation. The parameter τ is interpretable as a log ratio in expected event-free time at horizon L .

3.2.3 Semiparametric generalized additive models (GAMs)

To accommodate nonlinear covariate effects, the linear predictor in Equation (7) is generalized using smooth functions. Let pseudo_i denote the pseudo-observation for subject i (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen, 2010). The conditional mean structure is

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{pseudo}_i \mid A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i] = \alpha + \tau A_i + \sum_{k=1}^q f_k(Z_{ik}), \quad (12)$$

where $f_k(\cdot)$ are smooth functions (e.g., penalized regression splines). Equation (12) reduces to the linear model when each $f_k(\cdot)$ is replaced by a linear term. The treatment effect τ maintains the interpretation from the linear model. Estimation minimizes the penalized IPCW-weighted criterion

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \left\{ \text{pseudo}_i - \left(\alpha + \tau A_i + \sum_{k=1}^q f_k(Z_{ik}) \right) \right\}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^q \lambda_k \int (f_k''(z))^2 dz, \quad (13)$$

with λ_k controlling smoothness. Closed-form expressions for $\text{Var}(\hat{\tau})$ are generally unavailable in the presence of smooth terms; bootstrap-based inference is therefore used.

3.2.4 Models adjusted for dependent censoring

The IPCW in Equation (6) assumes independent censoring. With informative or competing censoring, this assumption fails and naive weighting may be biased. Wang and Schaubel (2018) propose decomposing the censoring process into K cause-specific components with cumulative hazards $\Lambda_k(t)$. Let $\hat{\Lambda}_k(t)$ denote their estimates. Define the composite IPCW for subject i as

$$w_i^* = \frac{\Delta_i}{\hat{S}_C(Y_i)} = \Delta_i \exp \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^K \hat{\Lambda}_k(Y_i) \right\}, \quad (14)$$

where $\hat{S}_C(t) = \exp\{-\sum_k \hat{\Lambda}_k(t)\}$ and $Y_i = \min(T_i, C_i, L)$. Equation (14) replaces Equation (6) when censoring is dependent. These adjusted weights replace w_i in all estimation criteria, yielding consistent estimates of τ under dependent or cause-specific censoring. Variance estimation uses a robust sandwich estimator that accounts for uncertainty in $\hat{\Lambda}_k(\cdot)$ and hence in w_i^* .

3.3 Variance estimation and asymptotic properties

Let $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\alpha, \tau, \boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top)^\top$ collect the regression parameters, and define the design vector $\mathbf{X}_i = (1, A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i^\top)^\top$. All models above can be written through the IPCW-weighted estimating equation

$$U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \mathbf{X}_i \{Y_i - m_L(A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta})\} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (15)$$

where $m_L(\cdot)$ denotes the specified mean structure (linear, stratified, or semiparametric), and w_i is either Equation (6) or (14). Under standard regularity conditions,

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{V}_\beta),$$

with asymptotic covariance

$$\mathbf{V}_\beta = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B} (\mathbf{A}^{-1})^\top, \quad \mathbf{A} = \mathbb{E} \left[-\frac{\partial U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}} \right], \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbb{E} \left[U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0) U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)^\top \right]. \quad (16)$$

Consistent estimators are

$$\widehat{\mathbf{V}}_\beta = \widehat{\mathbf{A}}^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{B}} (\widehat{\mathbf{A}}^{-1})^\top, \quad (17)$$

with

$$\widehat{\mathbf{A}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \mathbf{X}_i \left(\frac{\partial m_L(A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i; \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}} \right)^\top, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{B}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^2 \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \{Y_i - m_L(A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i; \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}})\}^2.$$

The variance of the estimated treatment effect is the (2, 2) element of $\widehat{\mathbf{V}}_\beta$, denoted $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\tau})$. When censoring is dependent (Section 3.2.4), $\widehat{\mathbf{B}}$ is augmented with the influence of $\hat{\Lambda}_k(\cdot)$ as in Wang and Schaebel (2018) to ensure valid inference.

Under regularity conditions,

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\tau} - \tau) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, \text{Var}(\hat{\tau})), \quad (18)$$

where $\text{Var}(\hat{\tau})$ is extracted from $\widehat{\mathbf{V}}_\beta$. A Wald statistic tests $H_0 : \tau = 0$,

$$Z_\tau = \frac{\hat{\tau}}{\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\tau})}} \stackrel{H_0}{\rightsquigarrow} \mathcal{N}(0, 1),$$

and two-sided confidence intervals are

$$\hat{\tau} \pm z_{1-\alpha/2} \sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\tau})},$$

where $z_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the upper $\alpha/2$ quantile of the standard normal distribution.

Estimating the censoring model (3.2.4) adds extra uncertainty. Following Wang and Schaebel (2018), we account for it by augmenting the sandwich covariance matrix in Equation (17). Specifically, the empirical variance component $\widehat{\mathbf{B}}$ is replaced by

$$\widehat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{adj}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (U_i(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) + \mathcal{I}_i^{(\Lambda)})(U_i(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) + \mathcal{I}_i^{(\Lambda)})^\top,$$

where $\mathcal{I}_i^{(\Lambda)}$ denotes the influence function contribution from the estimated cumulative hazard $\hat{\Lambda}_k(\cdot)$. This adjustment propagates the uncertainty in the censoring-model estimation into the variance of $\hat{\tau}$, supporting variance estimation under dependent censoring.

3.4 Core power calculation frameworks

A central design principle of `RMSTpowerBoost` is to offer two complementary frameworks for estimating power and required sample size: an analytical approximation for rapid exploration and a bootstrap-based method for simulation-driven calibration. This dual approach mirrors practical trial design workflows, where fast sensitivity analyses are followed by confirmatory validation.

3.4.1 Analytical method

The analytical method leverages the asymptotic normality of $\hat{\tau}$. For a total sample size N , the power is approximated as

$$\text{Power} = \Phi\left(\frac{|\tau|}{\sigma_N} - z_{1-\alpha/2}\right), \quad (19)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ denotes the standard normal cumulative distribution function, $\sigma_N = \sigma_1/\sqrt{N}$ is the standard error of $\hat{\tau}$ scaled to N , and $z_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the two-sided critical value at level α (e.g., 1.96 for $\alpha = 0.05$). This method is computationally efficient and suitable for preliminary design evaluation and sensitivity analysis.

3.4.2 Bootstrap method

The bootstrap approach avoids asymptotic assumptions by empirically approximating the sampling distribution of $\hat{\tau}$. By repeatedly resampling from pilot data, the empirical power is estimated as

$$\text{Power} = \frac{\text{Number of replicates with } p\text{-value} < \alpha}{n_{\text{sim}}}, \quad (20)$$

where n_{sim} is the number of bootstrap iterations. Although computationally intensive, this approach can be useful when analytic approximations are less reliable under complex censoring, nonlinear models, or heteroskedastic designs. The package implements both rapid `.analytical` functions for exploratory design and rigorous `.boot` routines for confirmatory assessment, with worked calls for each family presented in Section 4.

Together, these modeling frameworks—linear, stratified (additive and multiplicative), semiparametric, and dependent-censoring adjusted—form the statistical foundation of RMST-based power and sample size determination. All rely on the shared principle of IPCW-weighted estimation of conditional RMST regression models, providing coherent and flexible inference across a broad spectrum of trial designs.

4 Package Overview: Workflow and Design Inference

`RMSTpowerBoost` is organized around a study-design workflow in which the user starts from either an observed pilot data set or a generated pilot data set, chooses an RMST regression interface, and then calls either an analytical or a bootstrap design routine. To keep the overview concise, we show two complementary entry points only: an analytical workflow on a built-in R data set and a bootstrap workflow on a generated data set. Section 4 is therefore split into the scripted package overview in Section 4.1 and the companion graphical interface in Section 4.4. The code chunks in this section are shown for exposition and are not executed in the manuscript.

4.1 Analytical workflow with built-in data

An observed pilot data set can be recoded and passed directly to an analytical RMST design routine. The overview below uses `survival::veteran` and the linear IPCW interface (Section 3.2.1).

```
R> data(veteran, package = "survival")
R> vet <- within(veteran, {
+   arm <- ifelse(trt == 1, 0, 1)
+   status <- ifelse(status == 1, 1, 0)
+ })
R>
R> power_lin <- rmst.power(
+   Surv(time, status) ~ karno + age + diagtime + prior,
+   data = vet, arm = "arm",
+   sample_sizes = c(250, 300, 400, 500), L = 70)
```

This interface is appropriate when the pilot data already reflect the target study population and a large-sample design approximation is adequate.

4.2 Bootstrap workflow with generated data

When pilot data are unavailable, the package can first generate a pilot data set from a recipe and then pass that data set to a bootstrap-based design routine. The next overview uses a simulated multicenter data set and a multiplicative stratified sample-size search (Section 3.2.2).

```
R> ms_dat <- rmst.sim(  
+   n = 1600, model = "aft_weibull",  
+   baseline = list(shape = 1.25, scale = 11),  
+   treat_effect = -0.22,  
+   covariates = list(  
+     covar_continuous("age", mean = 62, sd = 9),  
+     covar_binary("sex", p = 0.48),  
+     covar_categorical("stage", probs = c(0.30, 0.50, 0.20),  
+       labels = c("I", "II", "III")),  
+     covar_continuous("x", dist = "lognormal", meanlog = 0, sdlog = 0.55),  
+     covar_categorical("center", probs = rep(1 / 18, 18),  
+       labels = paste0("C", sprintf("%02d", 1:18)))  
+   ),  
+   target_censoring = 0.22, seed = 101)  
R> ms_dat$center <- factor(ms_dat$center)  
R>  
R> ms_boot <- rmst.ss(  
+   Surv(time, status) ~ age + x,  
+   data = ms_dat, arm = "arm",  
+   strata = "center", strata_type = "multiplicative",  
+   target_power = 0.90, L = 50, type = "boot",  
+   n_sim = 100, n_start = 10, n_step = 10, parallel.cores = 2)
```

The same recipe-based workflow extends to the other simulation utilities `recipe_grid()`, `generate_recipe_sets()`, and `load_recipe_sets()`.

4.3 Returned objects and graphics

Each design function returns numerical summaries together with a package-generated `results_plot`. In the overview

```
R> power_lin$results_plot
```

```
R> ms_boot$results_plot
```

The remaining interfaces follow the same design pattern. In Section 5, we use the bootstrap GAM interface and the analytical dependent-censoring interface as two additional worked examples.

4.4 Shiny Interface

The companion Shiny application calls the same simulation, model-fitting, and design-calculation backend through a graphical interface. In practice, the app follows the same sequence as the code workflow in Section 4.1: users can supply pilot data or define a generation recipe, select one of the supported model classes,

choose either an analytical or a bootstrap design target, and inspect the returned tables and figures interactively. This interface is useful for screening truncation horizons, sample-size grids, and model choices before reproducing the final design in script form. Because the app delegates computation to the same package functions, results agree with the scripted workflow once the same arguments and random seed are used. The application is launched from R with

```
R> run_app()
```

Alternatively, a hosted web version of the application is available at

<https://arnab96.shinyapps.io/uthsc-app/>

and requires no local R installation. The web version is accessible from any modern browser and is pre-configured with all package dependencies, so users can upload pilot data or use the built-in data generator without any setup. Users who prefer to run computationally intensive bootstrap searches locally, apply a custom random seed for exact reproducibility, or integrate the application into an existing R workflow should use `run_app()`, which launches the identical interface with full access to local hardware.

5 Illustrative Examples

We now present two executed workflows that complement the two overview snippets. The first uses a built-in R data set and a bootstrap procedure. The second uses a generated data set and an analytical procedure. In both cases, the manuscript displays the package-generated results *plotobjects, with patchwork used only to place the two returned panels side*

5.1 GAM (Real data: survival::lung) – Bootstrap

We derive a two-arm contrast from sex, model age as a smooth effect (Section 3.2.3), and retain four additional covariates in linear form. Bootstrap power across candidate sample sizes is computed via `rmst.power` and a target sample-size search via `rmst.ss` for 80% power, both evaluated at $L = 2$ years. Figure 2 presents the Kaplan--Meier survival curves for the two treatment arms. Figure 3 reports the resulting design displays, with the empirical power curve on the left and the bootstrap search for the required sample size on the right.

```
R> power_gam <- rmst.power(  
+   Surv(time, status) ~ s(age) + ph.ecog + ph.karno + pat.karno + wt.loss,  
+   data = lung2, arm = "arm",  
+   sample_sizes = c(25, 50, 100), L = 2 * 365,  
+   n_sim = 100, parallel.cores = 2)
```

```
Error in `rmst.power()`:  
! could not find function "rmst.power"
```

```
R> ss_gam <- rmst.ss(  
+   Surv(time, status) ~ s(age) + ph.ecog + ph.karno + pat.karno + wt.loss,
```


Figure 2: Kaplan–Meier survival curves for the two treatment arms in the `survival::lung` data set. Arm 0 corresponds to male patients and arm 1 to female patients, as recoded from the `sex` variable. The curves are overlaid on the same axes to highlight between-arm differences in survival over the full follow-up period.

```
+ data = lung2, arm = "arm",
+ target_power = 0.80, L = 2 * 365,
+ n_sim = 100, patience = 5, parallel.cores = 2)
```

```
Error in `rmst.ss()`:
! could not find function "rmst.ss"
```

```
Error:
! object 'power_gam' not found
```

```
Error:
! object 'ss_gam' not found
```

```
Error:
! object 'gam_power_plot' not found
```

Figure 3: Bootstrap GAM workflow using `survival::lung`. The left panel shows the bootstrap power curve and the right panel shows the bootstrap sample-size search.

The two panels in Figure 3 provide complementary bootstrap summaries: the left panel shows how power changes over the candidate sample sizes, whereas the right panel converts the same model into a direct search for the required per-arm sample size.

5.2 Dependent censoring (Simulated) – Analytical

We simulate a two-arm trial in which censoring depends on baseline covariates, violating the independent-censoring assumption of the standard IPCW estimator.

Five covariates are generated: continuous age and bmi, binary sex, ordinal stage, and log-normal x. Event times follow a piecewise exponential proportional hazards model with decreasing baseline hazard rates over three intervals. Censoring is specified explicitly via a log-linear model on age, sex, and x, so that older, female, and high-x patients drop out earlier. The dependent-censoring adjusted estimator of Section 3.2.4 addresses this by re-weighting through estimated cause-specific cumulative hazards.

Step 1: Data generation.

```
R> cov_defs <- list(
+   covar_continuous("age", mean = 60, sd = 10),
+   covar_binary("sex", p = 0.50),
+   covar_continuous("bmi", mean = 27, sd = 4.5),
+   covar_categorical("stage", probs = c(0.40, 0.40, 0.20),
+     labels = c("I", "II", "III")),
+   covar_continuous("x", dist = "lognormal", meanlog = 0, sdlog = 0.50)
+ )
R>
R> rec_dc <- list(
+   n = 1800,
+   covariates = list(defs = cov_defs),
+   treatment = list(assignment = "randomization", allocation = "1:1"),
+   event_time = list(model = "ph_pwexp",
+     baseline = list(rates = c(0.08, 0.05, 0.03),
+       cuts = c(6, 24)),
+     effects = list(intercept = 0, treatment = -0.35,
+       covariates = list(age = 0.01, x = 0.02))),
+   censoring = list(
+     mode = "explicit",
+     administrative = list(time = 60),
+     dependent = list(formula = "~ age + sex + x",
+       beta = c("(Intercept)" = -3.2, age = 0.020,
+         sex = 0.250, x = 0.150))
+   ),
+   seed = 202
+ )
R>
R> dat_dc <- simulate_from_recipe(validate_recipe(rec_dc))
R> dc_covars <- c("age", "sex", "bmi", "x")
```

Step 2: Summary statistics. The pilot data set contains 1800 observations. Before fitting the design model we check arm balance with event and censoring counts, then examine whether the censoring rate differs by sex, the clearest binary indicator of dependent censoring in the recipe.

```
R> # arm balance: event and censoring counts
R> with(dat_dc, table(arm = arm, event = status))
```

```

event
arm  0  1
    0 40 875
    1 65 820

```

```

R> # censoring rate by sex -- confirms dependent censoring
R> round(with(dat_dc, tapply(1 - status, list(arm = arm, sex = sex), mean)), 3)

```

```

sex
arm    0    1
  0 0.036 0.051
  1 0.065 0.081

```

Female patients ($\text{sex} = 1$) are censored at a higher rate than male patients in both arms, consistent with the positive coefficient (+0.25) assigned to sex in the censoring model. This covariate-dependent dropout makes the standard IPCW estimator biased and motivates the adjusted estimator applied below. Figure 4 presents the Kaplan–Meier survival curves for the two arms, showing the between-arm separation induced by the simulated treatment effect.

Figure 4: Kaplan–Meier survival curves for the two treatment arms in the simulated dependent-censoring data set. The separation between arms reflects the negative treatment coefficient ($\tau = -0.35$) encoded in the piecewise exponential proportional hazards model. The curves are overlaid on the same axes to visualize the between-arm survival contrast across the follow-up horizon.

Step 3: Analytical power and sample-size search. We compute analytical power at $L = 120$ months via `rmst.power` with `dep_cens = TRUE` and then determine the sample size required to attain 95% power via `rmst.ss`, both using the dependent-censoring adjusted estimator of Section 3.2.4. Figure 5 summarizes these outputs, with the power curve on the left and the sample-size trajectory on the right.

```

R> dc_pow <- rmst.power(
+   Surv(time, status) ~ age + sex + bmi + x,

```

```
+ data = dat_dc, arm = "arm", dep_cens = TRUE,
+ sample_sizes = c(50, 100, 250), L = 120)
```

```
Error in `rmst.power()`:
! could not find function "rmst.power"
```

```
R> ss_dc <- rmst.ss(
+ Surv(time, status) ~ age + sex + bmi + x,
+ data = dat_dc, arm = "arm", dep_cens = TRUE,
+ target_power = 0.95, L = 120,
+ n_start = 50, n_step = 25, max_n = 600)
```

```
Error in `rmst.ss()`:
! could not find function "rmst.ss"
```

```
Error:
! object 'dc_pow' not found
```

```
Error:
! object 'ss_dc' not found
```

```
Error:
! object 'dc_power_plot' not found
```

Figure 5: Analytical dependent-censoring workflow based on generated pilot data. The left panel shows analytical power and the right panel shows the corresponding analytical sample-size search.

The left panel of Figure 5 shows the analytical power curve across candidate sample sizes under the dependent-censoring adjustment; the right panel translates the same fitted model into the required per-arm sample size for the target power level. Together, the three steps---data generation, descriptive verification of the dependent-censoring structure, and model-based design evaluation--- illustrate the full workflow from simulation recipe to study design conclusion.

Taken together, Sections 4 and 5 cover four complementary entry points to the package: analytical linear, bootstrap multiplicative stratified, bootstrap GAM, and analytical dependent-censoring design. We conclude in Section 6 by summarizing practical implications and outlining directions for extension.

6 Conclusion

The `RMSTpowerBoost` package provides tools for RMST-based power and sample size calculation in clinical study design. Built on IPCW-weighted estimation and semiparametric inference, it covers linear, stratified (additive and multiplicative), semiparametric GAM, and dependent-censoring regression models, with both analytical and bootstrap-based design procedures. The companion Shiny interface exposes the same computational engine through a graphical interface, supporting study design without direct coding. Returning to the motivations in Section 1, the central practical contribution

is that the same RMST framework can now be used for fast analytical screening, bootstrap validation, and interactive design exploration within one package.

Potential extensions include Bayesian formulations, adaptive trial designs, and integration with other survival modeling software. Large-sample properties and variance estimation details are given in the Appendix (Section A), beginning with the regularity conditions in Section A.1.

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A Appendix

This appendix sketches the large-sample arguments underlying the consistency and asymptotic normality of the RMST regression estimators summarized in Sections 3.3 and 3.4. The derivations follow the general IPCW and pseudo-observation frameworks for restricted mean survival time (Andersen et al., 2004; Parner and Andersen, 2010; Tian et al., 2014; Wang and Schaubel, 2018; Wang et al., 2019).

A.1 Regularity Conditions and Assumptions

The asymptotic results in Section 3.3 hold under standard conditions for right-censored regression estimated via inverse probability of censoring weighting (IPCW) or pseudo-observations. For completeness, we list the principal assumptions for the consistency and asymptotic normality of $\hat{\beta}$ and, in particular, of the treatment effect estimator $\hat{\tau}$.

- (A1) Independent and identically distributed observations. The observed tuples $\{(Y_i, \Delta_i, A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ are i.i.d. draws from the joint distribution of (T, C, A, \mathbf{Z}) . Here $Y_i = \min(T_i, C_i, L)$ and $\Delta_i = I(T_i \leq C_i, T_i \leq L)$.
- (A2) Independent (or conditionally independent) censoring. Censoring is independent of the event time conditional on covariates and treatment:

$$T \perp C \mid (A, \mathbf{Z}).$$

When this fails, the adjusted weighting scheme of Section 3.2.4 is used. The conditional censoring survival function $G(t \mid A, \mathbf{Z}) = P(C > t \mid A, \mathbf{Z})$ is strictly positive and consistently estimable on $[0, L]$.

- (A3) Correct mean specification (or pseudo-true target). The working mean model $m_L(A, \mathbf{Z}; \beta)$ satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}[\min(T, L) \mid A, \mathbf{Z}] = m_L(A, \mathbf{Z}; \beta_0)$$

for some β_0 . Under misspecification, $\hat{\beta}$ converges to the pseudo-true parameter minimizing the weighted squared loss, and the sandwich variance in Equation (17) remains valid for inference (Tian et al., 2014).

- (A4) Boundedness and integrability. The covariates and weights satisfy $\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{Z}\|^2] < \infty$ and $\mathbb{E}[w_i^2] < \infty$, with $G(t)$ bounded away from zero on $[0, L]$, ensuring $w_i = \Delta_i / \hat{G}(Y_i)$ is finite with high probability.
- (A5) Smoothness of the mean function. The mean $m_L(A, \mathbf{Z}; \beta)$ is continuously differentiable in β , with Lipschitz-continuous first derivatives in a neighborhood of β_0 . For GAMs, each smooth $f_k(\cdot)$ is twice continuously differentiable and the smoothing parameters $\lambda_k \rightarrow 0$ at an appropriate rate as $n \rightarrow \infty$ (Wood, 2017).
- (A6) Identifiability and non-collinearity. The design matrix $\mathbb{E}[w_i \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top]$ is positive definite, ensuring identification of β_0 . In stratified models, strata baselines are identified under standard centering/normalization constraints.

(A7) Regular estimating equation behavior. The estimating function $U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ in Equation (15) satisfies

$$\sqrt{n}U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{B}),$$

with $\mathbf{A} = \mathbb{E}[-\partial U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)/\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}]$ nonsingular. Then \sqrt{n} -consistency and asymptotic normality follow as in Equation (18).

Under these assumptions, IPCW-weighted estimators of the conditional RMST regression parameters are consistent and asymptotically normal. In practice, diagnostics (e.g., stability of $\hat{G}(Y_i)$ and checks of $m_L(\cdot)$ fit) are recommended to support the validity of the asymptotics.

A.2 Consistency

Under (A1)–(A4), the IPCW-weighted estimating equation

$$U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \mathbf{X}_i \{Y_i - m_L(A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta})\} = \mathbf{0}$$

satisfies $\mathbb{E}[U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)] = \mathbf{0}$, where $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$ denotes the (pseudo-)true parameter vector. By a uniform law of large numbers, $U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}) \rightarrow U(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \mathbb{E}[U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta})]$ uniformly in probability, and $U(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is continuous and uniquely zero at $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$. Thus, any solution $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ to $U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \mathbf{0}$ obeys

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \xrightarrow{p} \boldsymbol{\beta}_0,$$

implying $\hat{\tau} \xrightarrow{p} \tau$. Under misspecification, $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$ is the pseudo-true minimizer of the weighted squared error criterion (cf. Equation (8) for the linear case).

A.3 Asymptotic Normality

Let $\psi_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = w_i \mathbf{X}_i \{Y_i - m_L(A_i, \mathbf{Z}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta})\}$ denote the contribution to the estimating equation. A first-order Taylor expansion around $\boldsymbol{\beta}_0$ gives

$$\mathbf{0} = U_n(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) = U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0) + \left. \frac{\partial U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}^\top} \right|_{\boldsymbol{\beta}=\boldsymbol{\beta}_0} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0) + o_p(n^{-1/2}),$$

so that

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0) = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=1}^n \psi_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0) + o_p(1), \quad (21)$$

with $\mathbf{A} = \mathbb{E}[-\partial U_n(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)/\partial \boldsymbol{\beta}]$. By the multivariate central limit theorem,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=1}^n \psi_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{B}),$$

where $\mathbf{B} = \mathbb{E}[\psi_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)\psi_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_0)^\top]$. Substituting into (21) yields

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_0) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{A}^{-1})^\top),$$

establishing asymptotic normality. The variance of $\hat{\tau}$ is the (2,2) element of the sandwich covariance \mathbf{V}_β in Equation (16).

A.4 Influence Function Representation

When censoring is dependent, the IPCW weights w_i^* depend on estimated cumulative hazards $\hat{\Lambda}_k(t)$ from a censoring model (Section 3.2.4). Let $\mathcal{I}_i^{(\Lambda)}$ denote the influence function contribution from $\hat{\Lambda}_k(\cdot)$, evaluated at Y_i . Then the influence function of $\hat{\beta}$ is

$$\mathcal{I}_i^{(\beta)} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \left\{ \psi_i(\beta_0) + \mathcal{I}_i^{(\Lambda)} \right\},$$

satisfying $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{I}_i^{(\beta)}] = \mathbf{0}$ and $\text{Var}\{\mathcal{I}_i^{(\beta)}\} = \mathbf{V}_\beta$. This representation justifies augmenting $\hat{\mathbf{B}}$ in Equation (17) by the variability due to $\hat{\Lambda}_k(\cdot)$, as in Wang and Schaubel (2018).

A.5 Summary of Results

Under Assumptions (A1)–(A7), the IPCW-weighted estimators satisfy

$$\hat{\beta} \xrightarrow{p} \beta_0, \quad \sqrt{n}(\hat{\beta} - \beta_0) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B} (\mathbf{A}^{-1})^\top),$$

and the treatment effect estimator $\hat{\tau}$ admits influence function

$$\mathcal{I}_i^{(\tau)} = \mathbf{e}_2^\top \mathcal{I}_i^{(\beta)},$$

where \mathbf{e}_2 selects the component corresponding to τ . Consequently,

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\tau} - \tau) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, \text{Var}(\hat{\tau})),$$

providing the theoretical foundation for hypothesis testing, confidence interval construction, and analytical power calculations in Section 3.4.

A.6 Customization Reference

RMSTpowerBoost exposes a layered set of design choices that span the regression model, the inference method, the study parameters, and the data-generation recipe. The following describes each layer in full, with the available options listed explicitly.

Regression model. The five RMST regression models---linear (linear.*), additive stratified (additive.*), multiplicative stratified (MS.*), generalized additive (GAM.*), and dependent-censoring adjusted (DC.*)---are described in full in Section 3.2. Each family is accessed through consistently named functions that share the same argument interface, so the guidance below applies uniformly across all five.

Design inference method. As detailed in Section 3.4, each function family is available in an analytical variant (suffix .analytical), which derives power from the asymptotic normality of $\hat{\tau}$ and runs in seconds, and a bootstrap variant (suffix .boot), which approximates the sampling distribution empirically and is more robust when pilot samples are small or model structures are nonlinear. The number of bootstrap replicates is set via `n.sim`.

Core design parameters. Across all model families and inference methods, the following arguments govern the study design:

- `L` sets the RMST truncation horizon in the same time units as the observed data; the choice of `L` directly determines the treatment contrast being estimated and should reflect a clinically meaningful follow-up window.

- `sample_sizes` accepts a numeric vector of candidate per-arm sample sizes at which power is evaluated; evenly spaced grids work well for power curves, while targeted ranges near the expected required size reduce computation.
- `target_power` specifies the desired power level for sample-size search functions (e.g., 0.80 or 0.90); the search stops as soon as the estimated power first meets or exceeds this threshold.
- `n.start` and `n.step` define the starting per-arm sample size and the incremental step used by the sample-size search; smaller steps yield finer resolution but increase the number of model fits required.
- `max_n_per_arm` sets an upper bound on the search to prevent indefinite computation when the target power cannot be reached within a feasible sample.
- `patience` (bootstrap search only) is the number of consecutive steps without improvement after which the search terminates; increasing this value allows the algorithm to skip local fluctuations in the bootstrap power estimates.
- `parallel.cores` controls the number of processor cores used for parallel computation in bootstrap functions; setting this to the number of available physical cores typically provides the largest speed gain.

Covariate specification. The `linear_terms` argument accepts a character vector of column names from the pilot data that enter the model as linear predictors. In GAM functions, `smooth_terms` additionally accepts a character vector of column names to be modeled with penalized splines; the same variable may not appear in both vectors. In stratified models, `strata_var` identifies the column that defines stratum membership; it must be a factor or coercible to one before being passed to the function.

Simulation recipe. When pilot data are not available, `simulate_from_recipe()` generates a pilot data set from a declarative list that encodes the full data-generating process. The recipe exposes the following customization layers:

- `n` specifies the total sample size to generate.
- Each covariate in `covariates$defs` is described by its name, type ("continuous" or "categorical"), and `dist`, which may be "normal", "lognormal", "bernoulli", "ordinal", or "categorical"; the corresponding `params` list passes distribution-specific arguments such as mean and `sd` for normal, `p` for Bernoulli, or `prob` and `labels` for ordinal and categorical variables.
- Treatment assignment is specified under `treatment`. The field `assignment` controls the assignment mechanism, for example "randomization" for simple randomization, while `allocation` sets the arm ratio, for example "1:1" for balanced arms.
- The event-time model is selected via `event_time$model`, with currently supported options being "ph.pwexp" for a piecewise exponential proportional hazards model and "aft.weibull" for a Weibull accelerated failure time model. The baseline sub-list supplies model-specific parameters: for "ph.pwexp", the `rates` vector and `cuts` vector define the piecewise constant hazard on the specified

intervals; for "aft_weibull", shape and scale define the Weibull baseline. Log-linear covariate effects are provided through `effects$covariates` as a named list of coefficients, with `effects$treatment` giving the treatment coefficient.

- Censoring is controlled under `censoring$mode`, which accepts "target_overall" to calibrate an administrative censoring time so that the overall censoring proportion matches a user-specified target value, or "explicit" to define a fully specified censoring distribution. In explicit mode, `administrative$time` sets the administrative end of follow-up, and the optional dependent sub-list accepts a formula string and a beta named vector to induce covariate-dependent dropout via a log-linear censoring hazard.
- `seed` inside the recipe fixes the random seed for the generation step, ensuring reproducibility independently of the ambient R session seed.

Before passing a recipe to `simulate_from_recipe()`, validate it with `validate_recipe()`. This check enforces internal consistency and returns informative error messages for missing or incompatible fields. Batch utilities `recipe_grid()`, `generate_recipe_sets()`, and `load_recipe_sets()` extend this workflow to large parameter sweeps, as noted in Section 4.1.

Output and visualization. As described in Section 4, every design function returns a named list containing a `results_plot` ggplot2 object together with numerical summaries. The plot can be modified with any standard ggplot2 layer function (e.g., `ggplot2::labs()`, `ggplot2::theme()`) or combined side by side with other panels using `patchwork`, as illustrated in Section 5.